

Synthesis and Ion Exchange Properties of Cerium(IV) Tellurite

SYED ASHFAQ NABI* and RIFAQAT ALI KHAN RAO

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 001

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Cerium(IV) tellurite has been synthesized as a new inorganic cation exchanger by mixing solutions of cerium(IV) ammonium sulphate and tellurous acid of different concentrations and at different pH values. Ion exchange capacity of sample 5 at pH=6 is 0.90 meq/dry gm for Na⁺ ions. The chemical composition, thermal and chemical stability, pH titrations, ir studies, thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis have also been performed. Cerium tellurite is found to be chemically more stable than chromium tellurate.

SYNTHESIS of new inorganic ion exchangers is always of interest since they are specific in nature and can solve diverse problems of analytical chemistry and other fields. Synthesis of some rare earth metal tellurides have been reported in the literature¹ but their ion exchange properties have not been investigated. Zirconium tellurate², lanthanum tellurate³, titanium tellurate and chromium tellurate⁴ have been studied as ion exchangers in a cursory manner. However, tellurite of metals have not yet been studied as ion exchange materials. Phosphate⁵, arsenate⁶, tungstate⁷, molybdate⁸ and antimonate⁹ of cerium(IV) have been found to exhibit reasonable ion exchange properties. We, therefore, decided to synthesize cerium(IV) tellurite as a new cation exchanger and to investigate its properties in a systematic manner. The findings are presented in this paper.

Experimental

Reagents: Cerium(IV) ammonium sulphate (BDH) and sodium tellurite (BDH, Poole, England) were used. Other chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

Apparatus: Spectrophotometric studies were performed using Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer. An ELICO model LI-10 pH meter was used for pH measurement. Perkin-Elmer Model-137 spectrophotometer and Stanton

thermobalance type H₄ were used for ir and thermogravimetric studies.

Preparation of solutions: Cerium(IV) ammonium sulphate solution was prepared by dissolving required amount in distilled water. Tellurous acid solution was prepared by dissolving sodium tellurite in sufficient quantity of distilled water and gradually adding concentrated nitric acid or sulphuric acid to it. A white precipitate appeared in the beginning which redissolved in slight excess of acid. The solution was then made upto the required volume.

Synthesis: Samples of cerium(IV) tellurite were prepared by mixing solutions of tellurous acid with aqueous solutions of cerium(IV) ammonium sulphate in different volume ratios and at different pH values as shown in Table 1. The precipitates formed were allowed to settle for 24 hrs, washed several times with demineralized water, filtered and dried at 40°. The products were immersed in water when they broke down into smaller particles. The materials were then immersed in one molar nitric acid for 24 hrs to convert them into H⁺ form. The excess acid was removed by repeated washing with demineralized water and finally dried at 40°. The conditions of synthesis, ion exchange capacity and physical appearance of the materials are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1--SYNTHESIS AND SOME PROPERTIES OF CERIUM(IV) TELLURITE

Sample No.	Conditions of Synthesis			pH	Ion exchange capacity meq/g	Appearance of the bead in H ⁺ form	
	Concentration of cerium(IV) M	Concentration of Tellurous acid M	Acid used for preparation of Tellurous acid				
1	0.05	0.10	H ₂ SO ₄	1:1	0.0	0.44	Red, glassy
2R*	0.05	0.10	H ₂ SO ₄	1:1	0.0	0.42	Yellow, Chalky
3	0.05	0.10	HNO ₃	1:1	1.0	0.80	Yellow, hard
4	0.05	0.05	HNO ₃	1:1	7.0	0.00	Yellow, hard
5	0.05	0.05	HNO ₃	1:1	0.0	0.86	Orange, glassy
6	0.02	0.02	HNO ₃	1:3	0.0	0.44	Yellow, hard

R* = Refluxed in one molar H₂SO₄ for one hr.

Ion-exchange capacity : The ion exchange capacities of the samples were determined by column operations. The sample in H^+ form was placed in the column with glass wool support. H^+ ions were then eluted with one molar cation solution and determined titrimetrically with standard sodium hydroxide solution.

Chemical stability : The chemical stability of sample 5 was determined by shaking 500 mg of the sample with 50 ml of the solvent at room temperature ($25 \pm 1^\circ$) for 6 hrs and then keeping for 24 hrs. Cerium(IV) and tellurium released in the solvent were then determined spectrophotometrically using 1,10 phenanthroline¹⁰ and potassium iodide¹¹ method respectively.

Composition : A 500 mg of the sample was dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid. Cerium(IV) and tellurium were then determined by standard methods¹².

pH titrations : pH titrations for sample 5 were performed using the method of Topp and Pepper¹³. A 500 mg of the material in H^+ form was equilibrated with 50 ml of the solution for 6 hrs at room temperature ($25 \pm 1^\circ$). pH titration curves for LiCl-LiOH, NaCl-NaOH and KCl-KOH systems are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. pH titration curve of cerium(IV) tellurite.

IR spectra : The IR spectra of sample 5 dried at different temperatures were obtained by KBr disc method.

Thermal treatment : Thermogravimetric analysis and differential thermal analysis (DTA) of sample 5 in H^+ form were performed at a heating rate of $10^\circ/\text{min}$. The material was heated at various temperatures for one hr in a muffle furnace to examine the effect of drying temperature on ion exchange capacity and IR spectra.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows that the concentrations of the reagents and the type of the acid used for the preparation of cerium(IV) tellurite have no

significant effect on the ion exchange capacity of the product. However, the pH at which the preparation of the product is carried out affects the ion exchange capacity considerably. The product obtained at pH 7 shows no ion exchange properties. Sample 5 has been chosen for detailed studies because of its highest ion exchange capacity and apparently greater chemical stability as compared to the other samples.

The hydrogen ion liberation capacities for different mono and bivalent ions have been determined by column operation at $pH \approx 6$. The ion exchange capacities in meq/g for various metal ions are as follows: Li^+ , 0.44; Na^+ , 0.66; K^+ , 0.48; Rb^+ , 0.40; Mg^{+2} , 0.42; Ca^{+2} , 0.41 and Ba^{+2} , 0.26. It is interesting to note that the values of ion exchange capacities for Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ ions determined by column operation are found to be lower than those calculated from the titration curves (Fig. 1). This may be due to slow exchange process in column operation method which results in an incomplete elution of H^+ ions.

The pH titration curves apparently show three regions showing polyfunctional weak acid behaviour of cerium(IV) tellurite. The three regions are more clearly indicated in Li^+ and K^+ systems. A similar behaviour was observed in the case of lanthanum-tellurate⁸ and can be explained in the same manner.

The absorption sequence of alkali metals in different regions are as follows: (i) below pH 5.6: $K^+ > Na^+ > Li^+$, (ii) from pH 5.6 to 11.1: $K^+ > Li^+ > Na^+$ and (iii) above pH 11.2: $K^+ = Li^+ > Na^+$. It is interesting to note the Na^+ ion absorption capacity for lanthanum tellurate and cerium(IV) tellurite at pH 5.8. The absorption capacity in the case of cerium(IV) tellurite is much greater (0.90 meq/g) as compared to that in the case of lanthanum tellurate (0.16 meq/g).

The effect of drying temperatures on ion exchange capacity was also studied and the ion exchange capacities (meq/dry gm) for Na^+ ions at 40° , 100° , 200° , 300° , 400° , 500° , 600° and 800° are found to be 0.66, 0.60, 0.36, 0.30, 0.20, 0.08, 0.02 and 0.02 respectively.

It has been found that cerium(IV) tellurite is quite stable in water, acetic acid, formic acid and fairly stable in low concentrations of hydrochloric acid and nitric acid. The amount of exchanger dissolved (mg/50 ml) in different solvents is found to be: water, 1.5; 0.1M acetic acid, 2.7; 1.0M formic acid, 4.0; 0.1M citric acid, 2.1; 0.1M oxalic acid, 4.4; 2.0M ammonium nitrate, 2.8; 0.1M hydrochloric acid, 3.1; 1.0M hydrochloric acid, 7.7 and 2.0M nitric acid, 9.8. Cerium(IV) tellurite is found to be chemically more stable than chromium tellurate⁴ as the latter is fairly soluble in almost all mineral acids.

The IR spectra of sample 5 in H^+ form dried at various temperatures have been recorded. Three peaks are observed in the regions $900-1100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1550-1650 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $3000-3600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The 1st peak

in the region $900-1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a maximum at 1050 cm^{-1} may be due to the metal-oxygen stretching¹⁴. The second sharp peak at 1620 cm^{-1} may be due to the external water molecules. The third broad peak in the region $3000-3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ appears to be the characteristic of interstitial water molecules and OH groups. It is observed that the peak at 1620 cm^{-1} diminishes as the drying temperature of the material is increased above 100° . This is probably due to the removal of external water molecules. The disappearance of the peak in the region $3000-3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectrum of the material dried at 800° is also observed and may be due to conversion into oxides.

The chemical analysis of sample 5 shows the molar ratio of Ce : Te as 1 : 1.

The DTA curve of sample 5 in H^+ form shows two endothermic peaks at 130° and 450° and an exothermic peak at 500° (Fig. 2). The TGA curve shows continuous loss in weight upto 650° . The weight loss upto 160° (4%) seems to correspond

with the removal of external water molecules which is also indicated in the form of the endothermic peak in the DTA curve. Further weight loss in the region $160^\circ-450^\circ$ may be assigned to the loss of structural water molecules due to condensation of OH groups. The continuous loss in ion exchange capacity in the temperature range also support this conclusion. The loss in weight above 450° may be due to the decomposition of the material. Appearance of an exothermic peak in the region $450^\circ-650^\circ$ indicates this transition. The weight becomes constant after 650° due to the formation of stable oxide and the capacity reduced almost to a negligible value.

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Fig. 2. DTA and TGA curves of cerium(IV) tellurite.